

Synopsis from an Editor

Introduction

International Robotics & Automation Journal (IRATJ) is an international scholarly, peer review, open Access journal, initiated with an aim to promote the research and development in Robotics & Automation technology and technology breakthrough.

Peer Review Process

Peer review plays a very important role in ensuring the integrity of the scholarly record for our system. The process depends on a large extent on trust, and requires that everyone involved behaves responsibly and ethically. Peer reviewers play a central and critical part in the peer-review process. We get at least two independent reviews of each full length article and at least one for short report letters. We use a double-blind reviewing process in which author's and reviewer's identities are concealed. Our reviewers are encouraged to provide substantive, constructive reviews that provide suggestions for improving the work and distinguish between mandatory and non-mandatory recommendations. The handling editor considers all the returned reviews before making an overall decision. If the reviews differ widely, the editor may invite an additional reviewer so as to get an extra opinion before making a decision.

Ethical Standards

We at MedCrave take Ethics very seriously. We think Ethics should be followed to get better results not only in professional but also in our personal life. We accept manuscripts for publication only if it is made clear that investigations were carried out to a high ethical standard.

Advantages of International Robotics & Automation Journal (IRATJ)

International Robotics and Automation Journal (IRATJ) have already many theoretical, computational, experimental and practical aspects of autonomous systems, and/or modules of such systems. This journal is very broadly classified in not only in design, construction, operation, and use of robots, as well as computer systems for their control, sensory feedback and information processing systems. That being said we also go beyond industrial, domestic/household, medical, and service, military, entertainment, space, hobby and competition robot developments for instance manipulation robotic system, mobile robotics, data acquisition and control robotic system. Because of the complexity and broad nature of our journal, if for some reason we were not able to fit your article into our International Robotics & Automation Journal we may be able to create a brand new Robotics journal specific to the technology if the article is breakthrough technology.

How does International Robotics & Automation Journal beneficial for Authors?

- a. There are many advantages for authors and researchers for instance we provide free Pdf for open source articles,

Editorial

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Questions for Authors

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Feedback System

Here at MedCrave we take feedback seriously especially at International Robotics and Automation Journal and we think that we can improve system based on not just on article submission but also through recommendations, opinions, reviews, suggestions and other ideas that helps to move forward with research and development.